

**University of
Sheffield**

**Modelling indoor Heat Stress in Care Homes to
Enhance Health-Alerts and Planning.**

By:

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A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree
of Master of Science in Sustainable Architecture Studies

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This dissertation is dedicated to my mother and Father.
Thank you for always being there for me and supporting me.

Declaration

I, Shardul Bhushankumar Moholkar, confirm that the research presented in this dissertation for the degree of Master of Science in Sustainable Architecture Studies was conducted by me. The study is based on previous research, simulations, and data analysis. No interviews, surveys, or interactions with vulnerable individuals or sensitive subjects were involved in this research. Therefore, additional ethics approval was not required for the completion of this study.

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Abstract

The increasing frequency and intensity of heatwaves, exacerbated by climate change, pose significant health risks, particularly to vulnerable populations such as the elderly in care homes. While existing heat-health warning systems primarily focus on outdoor temperatures, they often fail to account for the critical indoor environments where these at-risk individuals spend most of their time. This dissertation addresses this gap by developing a model to assess indoor heat stress within Burnt Tree Croft Care Home, using DesignBuilder software to simulate indoor climatic conditions based on meteorological data from Sheffield.

The study calibrates the model with real-world data to accurately reflect the indoor environment, focusing on air temperature and relative humidity—the key factors influencing the Heat Index (HI). Custom HI thresholds were established, specifically tailored to indoor conditions, to trigger early and proactive interventions. These thresholds were used to develop a set of four-tiered action cards designed to guide care home staff in mitigating heat stress risks effectively. The action cards were validated through simulation results, showing that early interventions could significantly reduce the risk of heat-related illnesses among residents during extreme heat events.

This research contributes to the understanding of indoor heat stress management by emphasizing the importance of indoor-specific heat-health warning systems. The findings suggest that current outdoor-based warning systems are insufficient for safeguarding vulnerable populations in care homes and that the integration of indoor data into these systems is crucial. Recommendations for policy and practice include the implementation of tailored indoor heat-health alerts, regular monitoring of indoor conditions, and the development of building improvements to enhance thermal resilience. The study also highlights the need for further research with comprehensive data collection and a broader scope to fully validate and generalize the proposed interventions.

Table of Contents

Declaration.....	i
Acknowledgements.....	ii
Abstract.....	iii
List of Figures	vi
1. Introduction.....	1
1.1 Background.....	1
1.2 Problem Statement	1
1.3 Goals.....	2
2. Literature Review	4
2.1 Understanding Heat Stress in Indoor Environments, Particularly in Care Homes	4
2.2 The Role of Building Characteristics and Urban Microclimates in Indoor Heat Stress	7
2.3 Challenges and Limitations of Current Heat-Health Warning Systems.....	8
2.4 Enhancing Heat-Health Warning Systems Through Indoor Heat Exposure Quantification...	10
2.5 Importance of Action Plans and New Action Cards in Heat-Health Management.....	11
2.6 Conclusion	12
3 Methodology	13
3.1 Research Design	13
3.1.1 Simulation-Based Approach	13
3.2 Case Study: Burnt Tree Croft Care Home.....	13
3.2.1 Selection Rationale.....	14
3.2.2 Building Characteristics and Environmental Conditions	14
3.3 Data Collection.....	17
3.3.1 Meteorological Data.....	17
3.3.2 Indoor Climate Data.....	19
3.4 Simulation Process	21
3.4.1 Introduction to Building Energy Simulation (BES)	21
3.4.2 Simulation calibration methods	22
4 Results.....	25

4.1 Calibration Results	25
4.1.1 Summary of Calibration Metrics:	25
4.1.2 Comparison of Simulated and Measured Air Temperatures:	25
4.2 Final Simulation Outcomes	26
4.2.1 Temperature Analysis:	26
4.3 Heat Index Analysis	28
4.3.1 Heat Index Calculation.....	29
4.4 Identification of Heat Stress Risk Zones	31
5 Development of Action Cards for Indoor Heat Index Thresholds	34
5.1 Rationale for Custom HI Thresholds	34
5.2 Custom Heat Index Thresholds.....	35
5.3 Proposed Action Cards	36
5.4 Validation Through Simulation and Literature Review	37
5.4.1 Simulation Results:	37
5.4.2 Supporting Literature:	37
5.4.3 Justification of Custom Action Cards	37
5.4.4 Enhanced Protection for Vulnerable Populations:	38
5.4.5 Implementation Strategies:	38
6 Discussion.....	39
6.1 Interpretation of Key Findings	39
6.2 Limitations of the Study.....	39
6.3 Recommendations for Future Research	40
7 Conclusion	41
7.1 Summary of Key Findings	41
7.2 Significance of the Study	41
7.3 Recommendations for Policy and Practice	42
7.4: Final Thoughts and Future Directions	43
8 References:.....	45

List of Figures

Figure 1 Excess Mortality by Age Group during Heat Periods (1 June to 31 August 2022) (Source: ONS).....	4
Figure 2: Health Issues Related to Indoor Heat Stress in Elderly Populations	6
Figure 3 UK Health Security Agency (Source: Author)	9
Figure 4 The Burnt Tree Croft Lower Ground Floor (Source: Author).....	15
Figure 5 The Burnt Tree Croft Ground Floor (Source: Author).....	15
Figure 6 The Burnt Tree Croft First Floor (Source: Author).....	16
Figure 7 The Burnt Tree Croft Lower Second Floor (Source: Author).....	16
Figure 8 Frame Work of Research Methodology And Steps of The Study (Source: Author)	18
Figure 9: Measured Air Temperature and Relative Humidity for Bedroom 11 (Ground Floor) (Source: Design Builder).....	20
Figure 10 : Measured Air Temperature and Relative Humidity for Bedroom 39 (Second Floor) (Source: Design Builder).....	20
Figure 11 Frame Work of Process of Calibration and Validation (Source: Author).....	21
Figure 12: The MBE and CV(RMSE) values for air temperature calibration (Source: Author).....	26
Figure 13: Simulated Air Temperature of year 2022 Heat wave (Source: Author)	27
Figure 14: Simulated Air Temperature of year 2022 Heat wave (Source: Author)	27
Figure 15: Heat Index (HI) for each bedroom on July 19th 2022 (Source: Author).....	30
Figure 16: : Heat Index (HI) for each bedroom on July 19th 2022 (Source: Author).....	30
Figure 17: : Heat Index (HI) for each bedroom on July 19th 2022 (Source: Author).....	31
Figure 18: Heat Map (Source: Author).....	33

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The problems created by extreme weather events caused by climate change, especially heatwaves, even in historically heating-dominant nations like the UK ([Norhan Bayomi and Fernández, 2023](#)), are the root of the motivations expressed to address the study topics related to indoor heat stress in care Homes. This group is at higher risk due to multiple factors coming together, which include physiological changes associated with ageing, pre-existing health issues, and limited mobility. In recent times, the UK, which is often recognised for its moderate climate, has had severe heat occurrences, such as the heatwave in July 2022. This has emphasized the need for improved techniques to control the heat in care facilities. ([Fischer and Schär, 2010](#)) ([McMichael, Woodruff and Hales, 2006](#))

Heat-Health Alert Systems (HHAS) are meant to help handle extreme heat. However, these systems primarily concentrate on outdoor conditions and neglect the specific indoor settings where vulnerable populations, like the elderly in care homes, spend most of their time. The discrepancy between interior and outside temperatures may be substantial, with indoor conditions sometimes reaching hazardous levels before external temperatures prompting alarms ([Hong et al., 2021](#); [Schiano-Phan, Weber and Santamouris, 2015](#)).

1.2 Problem Statement

The majority of the existing warning systems that are focused on the impacts of heat on individuals are mostly dependent on the temperatures outdoors. The indoor atmosphere at care homes, particularly those where elderly people spend most of their time, is not taken into full consideration by these individuals. Laouadi et al. (2023) and Tartarini et al. (2017) research indicate that building design, insulation quality, and urban microclimate can worsen heat stress and lead to major health issues. The absence of this information in the warning system is crucial as it could delay critical assistance and increase the risk of heat-related illnesses and deaths among care home residents. A significant portion of the present structure of heat-health warning systems is based on thresholds that are generated from data collected from the temperature outside. On the other hand, these technologies are not enough to handle the complex dynamics of indoor climates, particularly in residential care facilities where senior people spend a considerable amount of time inside the building. Indoor settings, which are impacted by elements such as building design, insulation quality, and urban microclimates, may considerably worsen heat stress, leading to serious health

implications ([Laouadi et al., 2023](#); [Tartarini et al., 2017](#)). These results stem from a prior study. This void in the alarm system is very important because it has the potential to postpone actions that are required and to raise the risk of heat-related illness and death among residents of senior care facilities.

1.3 Goals

The primary goals of this study encompass:

- Using meteorological data from Sheffield, we are simulating the interior climatic conditions at Burnt Tree Croft Care Home.
- Determining the specific locations inside the care home that are most vulnerable to heat stress during periods of high temperatures.
- Setting heat stress levels and suggesting a four-tiered action plan to reduce the dangers for inhabitants.

The purpose of these goals is to close the disparity between heat alarm systems that are based on external circumstances and the real inside conditions that impact the health of people.

1.4 Research Aim and Question

The research question identified from the existing gap is:

- How can the Heat-Health Warning System be enhanced to better reflect the indoor environmental conditions in care homes during heatwaves?

The research aim to address this question is:

To enhance the accuracy and responsiveness of Heat-Health Warning Systems by integrating data on indoor environmental conditions, simulated using DesignBuilder, to better protect elderly residents in care homes during periods of extreme heat.

The research objectives to achieve this aim include:

- Simulate indoor climatic conditions within Burnt Tree Croft Care Home using Sheffield's meteorological data during heatwave events through DesignBuilder software.
- Identify specific zones within the care home that are particularly vulnerable to heat stress, based on the simulation outputs.
- Define heat stress thresholds informed by the simulation data and propose a four-tiered action plan, including new action cards, to manage and mitigate identified risks.
- Emphasize the necessity of these action cards as essential tools for care home staff, ensuring they can proactively manage heat stress with appropriate and timely responses.
- Provide recommendations to bridge the gap between outdoor-based Heat-Health Warning Systems and the actual indoor conditions that affect residents' health, leading to a more comprehensive and responsive alert system.

The dissertation consists of six chapters. Chapter 1 represents an introduction, while Chapter 2 provides an overview of the existing literature on the issue, detects a gap in the study's findings, and develops the research question, goals, and purposes of the study. The approach is discussed in Chapter 3. We provide the techniques used for gathering and examining the data. Chapter 4 outlines the main discoveries. Chapter 5 presents a detailed examination and interpretation of the collected data, using the used research techniques. Completely. Chapter 6 provides a summary of the main discoveries, the constraints of the research, and suggestions for further action.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Understanding Heat Stress in Indoor Environments, Particularly in Care Homes

The frequency and severity of heat waves have led to a growing public health concern around heat stress, particularly in interior locations such as care facilities. Care home elderly are particularly vulnerable to heat-related disorders such as heat stroke, heat fatigue, and exacerbation of other medical conditions including heart diseases. There is inadequate temperature management leading to lesser sweating rates hence exposure to these patients' chronically ill people who move with difficulty have more chances of developing complications ([Cedeño-Laurent et al., 2018](#); [Lundgren-Kownacki et al., 2018](#)).

Recent mortality data further emphasizes the hazards linked with heat stress in care facilities. During the heatwave from June 1 to August 31, 2022, England and Wales saw an 8.2% increase in fatalities compared to the average. The elderly, especially those residing in care facilities, saw a disproportionate effect, highlighting the lethal consequences of excessive heat on this susceptible demographic ([ONS, 2022](#)). The statistics provided by the Office for National Statistics (ONS) emphasise the need to manage heat stress in care facilities, where people cannot frequently independently adopt preventative measures.

Figure 1 Excess Mortality by Age Group during Heat Periods (1 June to 31 August 2022) (Source: ONS)

To further illustrate the health risks associated with indoor heat stress in elderly populations, Below provides an overview of the key health issues and their impacts.

Health Issue	Description	Impact on Elderly Population	References
Heat Exhaustion	A condition characterized by heavy sweating, weakness, dizziness, and nausea.	Can lead to more severe heat-related illnesses if not treated promptly.	(Basu, 2002)
Heatstroke	A life-threatening condition where the body temperature rises above 40°C (104°F).	Elderly individuals are more susceptible due to impaired thermoregulation.	(Leon and Helwig, 2010)
Dehydration	Loss of body fluids due to excessive sweating.	Can exacerbate existing health conditions and lead to confusion or fainting.	(Weinberg, 1995)
Hyponatremia	Low sodium levels in the blood are caused by excessive sweating and fluid intake.	Can lead to neurological symptoms such as confusion, seizures, and coma.	(Verbalis et al., 2013)
Cardiovascular Stress	Increased strain on the heart and blood vessels.	Can exacerbate conditions like hypertension, heart failure, and arrhythmias.	(Epstein and Yanovich, 2019)
Respiratory Problems	Breathing difficulties due to heat and humidity.	Can worsen chronic conditions like COPD and asthma, leading to respiratory distress.	(Barreca, 2012)
Kidney Failure	Impaired kidney function due to dehydration and heat stress.	Elderly individuals are at higher risk, especially those with pre-existing kidney issues.	(Roncal-Jimenez et al., 2015)
Heat Rash	Irritation of the skin caused by excessive sweating.	Though not life-threatening, it can cause discomfort and lead to infections if severe.	(Mayo Clinic, n.d.)

Agitation and Confusion	Cognitive symptoms triggered by heat stress, especially in those with dementia.	Can lead to behavioural changes, increased risk of accidents, and difficulty in care.	(Tartarini et al., 2017)
Hyperthermia	Abnormally high body temperature not due to fever.	Can lead to severe health complications, including organ failure and death.	(Vassallo, Gera and Allen, 1995)
Thrombosis	Formation of blood clots due to dehydration and immobility.	Increases the risk of strokes and heart attacks, particularly in immobile elderly patients.	(Kim et al., 2014)
Increased Mortality	Elevated risk of death due to the cumulative effects of heat stress.	Mortality rates rise significantly during heatwaves, especially in care homes.	(Gasparrini et al., 2015)

Figure 2: Health Issues Related to Indoor Heat Stress in Elderly Populations

The study conducted by Laouadi et al. (2023) examines the dangers of excessive heat in long-term care facilities. The research focuses on creating precise guidelines to evaluate these risks and determining particular temperature limits that, if surpassed, may seriously endanger the health of senior residents. This study is essential because it not only points out the limitations of conventional cooling methods, such as natural ventilation but also emphasizes the need for improved thermal management systems that can function properly in severe temperatures. These solutions are essential for protecting vulnerable persons in care settings, since conventional methods may not be effective ([Laouadi et al., 2023](#)).

Tartarini et al. (2017) provide more information by analyzing how variations in indoor temperature can influence the behaviour and well-being of dementia patients living in nursing homes. Their research indicated that even minor changes in indoor temperature can extremely increase agitation among residents indicating that consistency of the indoor environment is not only an issue of comfort but also part of healthcare for this movement. As stated by Tartarini et al., ensure goodness for those with cognitive issues who might not communicate their discomfort, therefore, this research shows how essential it is for care facilities to have precise temperature regulation to maintain wellbeing, especially for dementia sufferers. ([Tartarini et al., 2017](#))

Isaac L. Razo et al. (2024) explore the limitations of passive cooling strategies, such as enhanced ventilation and shading, in care homes during heatwaves. While these strategies are often considered environmentally friendly and cost-effective, the study suggests they may be insufficient during extreme heat events, particularly in urban areas affected by the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect. The researchers advocate for the integration of more robust HVAC systems to maintain safe indoor environments, arguing that these systems are essential in care settings where residents are at high risk of heat-related health complications. This research highlights the complex interplay between building design, environmental factors, and resident health, and underscores the need for comprehensive cooling strategies that go beyond passive measures ([Christopher et al., 2022](#))

2.2 The Role of Building Characteristics and Urban Microclimates in Indoor Heat Stress

The indoor thermal environment is significantly influenced by building design and characteristics, especially in urban areas. The Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect is a phenomenon where urban areas tend to be hotter than rural areas due to human activities and infrastructure. Schiano-Phan et al. (2015) noted that this effect can make indoor heat stress worse, especially in buildings located in highly urbanized areas with little greenery. These kinds of structures are most susceptible to excessive indoor temperatures because they absorb and hold more heat compared to their surroundings; hence, it becomes difficult to provide safe and pleasant indoor spaces during hot weather ([Schiano-Phan, Weber and Santamouris, 2015](#)).

To investigate how urban microclimates shape , building performance and occupant comfort , Hong et al. (2021) analyze different aspects of the environment. Compared to buildings located in areas with a high density of structures, those found close to green spaces that enjoys its cooling effects possess lower heat stress potentialities. This implies that architectural conservation programs with tree-lined streets and parks should be incorporated to alleviate UHI effect leading to more comfortable indoor environments during heat waves hence reducing pressure on mechanical cooling systems. The significance of this study is especially important for care homes which need design integration methods to regulate

indoor temperatures straightly through raising greenery parks along their perennial walls ([Hong et al., 2021](#)).

The material used in the construction of a building is fundamental for managing indoor thermal conditions. According to De Wilde & Coley (2012), heavy brick-built houses like concrete prevent them from heating up quickly under sunlight. Even if this is advantageous to some regions, it could be very wrong during extreme hot weather seasons where residential people are highly affected by it. Besides, delayed heat emission can make rooms too hot for comfort in the nighttime or evening hours when cooling alternatives may not work as required. According to de Wilde & Coley, this study highlights how crucial it is to take into account both the pros and cons of thermal mass through building materials especially in times of climate change when heatwaves continue becoming increasingly frequent and severe. ([de Wilde and Coley, 2012](#))

2.3 Challenges and Limitations of Current Heat-Health Warning Systems

Heat-health warning Systems (HHAS) are crucial for safeguarding public health during high-heat events. However, they encounter notable difficulties and constraints, especially when it comes to fulfilling the distinct requirements of interior settings in care homes. These systems primarily depend on external temperature thresholds to activate alarms, which do not adequately represent the conditions within buildings where sensitive groups, such as senior citizens, spend almost all of their time. Consequently, interior settings may attain dangerously high temperatures long before outside circumstances are considered severe enough to warrant issuing warnings, thereby leaving these people insufficiently safeguarded ([Casanueva et al., 2019](#)).

A recent example of this gap occurred on August 12, 2024 when the UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA) sent out an email alert. This alert gave general information on what the weather would be like during a heat wave that was about to hit the country, indicating that extreme heat and humidity were likely to be experienced especially in urban areas. Nevertheless, it failed to provide concrete measures which are necessary for the

management of uncomfortable temperatures within care homes. This omission is rather serious because it means that staff working in such places have no guidance on how they can keep their patients safe from dying due to excessive warmth (Source: Author).

Forecast issued by the Met Office on behalf of UKHSA on Monday, August 12, 2024 at 6:44 AM
View current Weather-Health Alerting situation

General overview of weather conditions in relation to the hazard (Heat) next 5 days

Very hot in places on Monday, with a wider area of low 30s degrees Celsius expected across the south and east compared to the past weekend, and with some places even reaching the mid-30s. There is some scope for sporadic cloud and thunderstorms to blunt the intensity somewhat, especially in the north and northwest of the area affected and perhaps later the east, but a hot day is expected widely, with a relatively humid feel given the easterly wind in many areas. A further very warm night should follow Monday into Tuesday. While still widely warm, Tuesday daytime should see a reduction in both the extent and intensity of the peak heat - with a progressive ingress of breezeier conditions and rain or showers in places from the west. In parts of the east, a further very warm night should follow into Wednesday, however this should herald a breezeier, more reliably unsettled end to the working week with warm, but more reasonable temperatures across England.

General overview of weather conditions in relation to the hazard (Heat) 6-15 days

Most likely changeable, with temperatures near average. A lower probability alternative scenario for the first few days of this period would see unsettled conditions pass further to the northwest of the UK, which would potentially draw up higher temperatures from the Continent for a time, however this is not the favoured outcome at present. For the remainder of August, conditions are most likely to be often unsettled, with no particularly strong signal for any prolonged dry weather. As a result, temperatures are expected to be most likely around or perhaps a little below average. This does not preclude some hotter spells, and should any occur these would most likely short-lived and across the south and/or east. The chances of alert criteria being challenged are no greater than normal for the time of year as a result of the above.

General overview of weather conditions in relation to the hazard (Heat) 16-30 days

As is typical for the season, signals as to predominant conditions weaken into early September, but a continuation of the conditions as described for the end of August (above) appears most probable. Again, the chances of alert criteria being challenged are no greater than normal for the time of year as a result of the above.

Region	Probability of reaching low impact threshold	General comments on weather
Next 5 6-15 16-30 days	days days days	

15/08/2024, 10:31

NE	30	20	5
NW	60	20	5
YH	80	20	10
EM	90	20	10
WM	90	20	10
EoE	90	20	10
Lon	90	20	10
SE	90	20	10
SW	70	20	10

Gmail - 2024-08-12 - Heat-Health Planning Advice from the Met Office

The most reliably sub-threshold region, warmest in the far south but probably tempered by thunderstorm activity.
Hottest in the major urban areas of the south on Monday, although marginal here. Markedly less hot and humid into Tuesday.
Hot and humid in the major urban areas of the South and West Ridings especially. Widely less hot and humid through Tuesday.
Very hot and humid on Monday, especially so in the east. This may be tempered locally by intense thunderstorms later. Becoming less hot and humid through Tuesday.
Hot and humid on Monday, especially in major urban centres and the south and east more generally. Markedly less hot and humid into Tuesday.
Very hot and humid on Monday, especially in a swathe from Greater London to the Fens, perhaps locally tempered by thunderstorms later. Becoming less hot and humid through to midweek, with more comfortable nights, although still warm to end the week.
Very hot and humid on Monday. Becoming less hot and humid through to midweek, with more comfortable nights, although still warm to end the week.
Very hot and humid on Monday, especially in the east near Greater London. Becoming less hot and humid through to midweek, with more comfortable nights, although still warm to end the week.
Hot and humid in the east on Monday, especially in major urban centres here, with the west of the region warm but much less markedly so. Less hot and humid generally into Tuesday. Remaining warm later in the week.

NE = North East | NW= North West | YH = Yorkshire and The Humber | EM = East Midlands | WM = West Midlands | EoE = East of England | Lon = London | SE = South East | SW = South West

For further information, please refer to the UKHSA Adverse Weather and Health Plan

All other enquiries can be directed to enquiries@ukhsa.gov.uk

Please do not reply to this email

This service is provided free of charge by the UK Health Security Agency and the Met Office.

Figure 3 UK Health Security Agency (Source: Author)

The absence of precise and comprehensive instructions for indoor settings in these notifications is not a mere oversight, but a significant defect that might result in serious repercussions. Without explicit guidance on how to modify interior conditions or which proactive actions to implement, care facilities may be ill-equipped to adequately address the rapid increase in internal temperatures. This deficiency may directly lead to higher rates of illness and death among senior inhabitants, who are already at an elevated risk during heatwaves. Hence, it is essential to reconsider and revamp HHAS to include explicit, practical approaches for handling indoor heat stress in care settings, guaranteeing that these surroundings do not turn into lethal hazards during severe heat events.

Further highlighting the absence of defined procedures for reducing heat warnings after the immediate danger has gone is done by Lowe et al. (2011). This may lead to extended periods of increased vigilance, which may not align with the real degree of danger, resulting in alert tiredness among care home personnel and residents. Fatigue may decrease the efficiency of warnings and lower the level of readiness for real crises, especially in care

homes where the capacity to quickly and efficiently adapt to changing situations is crucial ([Lowe, Ebi and Forsberg, 2011](#)).

In addition, Issa et al. (2021) contend that several current HHAS lack thorough adaptation techniques. Although these systems are successful in delivering alerts, they often lack the essential assistance for adopting adaptive actions, such as enhancing the thermal efficiency of buildings or boosting access to cooling centres. The existence of this gap is especially worrisome in care facilities, since the capacity to promptly adjust to changing circumstances is vital for safeguarding the health of patients. The need for stronger adaption methods, including enhancements in both infrastructure and operations, is apparent in light of the escalating frequency and severity of heat waves ([Issa et al., 2021](#)).

2.4 Enhancing Heat-Health Warning Systems Through Indoor Heat Exposure Quantification

For Heat-Health Warning Systems to be more relevant and effective, it is necessary to add data on indoor heat exposure. As Dóra Szagri, Nagy and Szalay explain, indoor conditions can provide a broader picture of the risk of heat stress than outdoor temperatures, especially for people living in care homes. The inclusion of indoor environmental data into HHAS can lead to more targeted and effective interventions with regard to vulnerable populations' health outcomes ([Dóra Szagri, Nagy and Szalay, 2023](#)). If these systems could measure indoor heat exposure accurately, they would be better placed to predict where and when heat stress risks are at their worst and thereby respond appropriately ([Dóra Szagri, Nagy and Szalay, 2023](#)).

Norhan Bayomi and Fernández (2023) propose the use of system dynamics models to better understand the interactions between indoor environmental conditions and the vulnerability of residents. These models, which incorporate real-time data and allow for the simulation of various scenarios, can provide more accurate predictions and support more effective planning and intervention strategies. By simulating different heatwave scenarios and their potential impact on indoor environments, these models can help care home managers identify the most vulnerable areas within their facilities and prioritize interventions accordingly ([Norhan Bayomi and Fernández, 2023](#)).

Laouadi et al. (2023) assert that integrating building simulations with bioheat models offers a strong foundation for establishing health-oriented criteria for indoor settings. These models have the ability to detect certain regions inside care homes that are most susceptible to overheating, enabling focused actions that effectively decrease the likelihood of heat-related diseases. By incorporating these models into HHAS, it becomes feasible to develop systems that are more dynamic and responsive. These systems not only forecast the occurrence of heat stress but also provide explicit instructions on how to alleviate its impacts ([Laouadi et al., 2023](#)).

2.5 Importance of Action Plans and New Action Cards in Heat-Health Management

One of the most important elements in improving Heat-Health Alert Systems (HHAS) is making sure that care home personnel have the necessary strategies and resources for effectively dealing with increased temperatures. It is necessary to design action plans with different levels of responses based on various components that cumulate into a single degree of heat stress in order to make sure that every intervention made is both timely as well as relevant during this period. These plans, when used effectively, have been found to reduce morbidity and mortality from heat by a considerable margin especially among vulnerable populations like the old persons ([Ebi et al., 2004](#); [Matthies et al., 2008](#)).

The introduction of **new action cards**—simplified, easy-to-follow tools that provide specific instructions based on the current heat stress level—can significantly improve the effectiveness of heat-health management in care homes. These cards can serve as quick reference guides for staff, helping them to quickly identify and implement the appropriate actions needed to protect residents during periods of extreme heat. Research has demonstrated the importance of having clear, accessible instructions for healthcare providers during heat events, as this can prevent delays in critical interventions ([G.R. McGregor et al., n.d.](#)).

In addition, the most recent studies on indoor thermal exposure should build these cards and also, they should be updated frequently as per the latest findings and recommendations. For example, WHO (World Health Organization) highlights that it is important for localities to frequently update their plans concerning heat-health in order to ensure that they are efficient ([Matthies et al., 2008](#)). These instruments can assist in ensuring that responses to heat stress remain stable and efficient among nursing facility employees by offering them with unambiguous actions. This will help decrease chances of people living there developing diseases resulting from high temperatures.

Well-designed action plans and action cards not only safeguard against immediate health hazards but also enhance the overall readiness of care facilities for different climate-related catastrophes. Research has shown that healthcare institutions that have well-developed heat-health action plans are more prepared to manage abrupt increases in heat-related health problems, which may strain emergency services ([van Loenhout et al., 2018](#)). Hence, it is essential to include these technologies into comprehensive disaster preparation strategies, guaranteeing that care facilities are well equipped to manage not just heatwaves but also other climate-related crises.

2.6 Conclusion

The literature reviewed here highlights the critical need for a more comprehensive approach to managing heat stress in care homes. Current Heat-Health Warning Systems, which are largely based on outdoor conditions, do not adequately protect vulnerable populations from the dangers of indoor heat stress. By integrating indoor environmental data, enhancing action plans, and introducing new action cards, these systems can be significantly improved, leading to better health outcomes for elderly residents during heatwaves. The integration of advanced modeling techniques, such as system dynamics and bioheat models, into HHAS represents a promising avenue for creating more responsive and effective heat-health strategies.

3 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study employs a combined research design, integrating simulation modelling with a case study approach to enhance the Heat-Health Warning System (HHWS) by incorporating indoor environmental data from care homes during heatwaves. This design is structured to address the critical gap between outdoor-based heat-health warnings and the actual conditions experienced by elderly residents indoors.

3.1.1 Simulation-Based Approach

Simulation modelling forms the core of this research, chosen for its capacity to replicate and analyse indoor environmental conditions under various external weather scenarios. Design Builder software, known for its robustness in simulating building performance, was utilized to model the thermal environment within Burnt Tree Croft Care Home. This software allows for precise control over variables such as temperature, humidity, and HVAC operations, which are critical in assessing heat stress in care homes ([Hong et al., 2021](#)).

The use of simulation is particularly valuable in predicting how indoor environments respond to extreme heat, providing insights that are essential for improving HHWS. Simulation modelling enables the manipulation of environmental factors within a controlled virtual environment, offering a detailed understanding of how these factors contribute to heat stress ([Attia et al., 2012](#)). This approach also facilitates the identification of critical areas within the care home that are most vulnerable to heat stress, which is vital for developing targeted interventions ([Ascione et al., 2014](#)).

3.2 Case Study: Burnt Tree Croft Care Home

The Burnt Tree Croft Care Home, which is located in Sheffield, United Kingdom, was chosen as the main point for this research because of its representative design and usual layout, both of which are typical of other care institutions located all throughout the nation. An in-depth investigation of the ways in which interior surroundings inside such facilities react to the effects of outdoor heat stress during severe weather events, notably heatwaves, is made possible by the selection of this care home as a case study.

3.2.1 Selection Rationale

The selection of Burnt Tree Croft Care Home was based on its excellent architectural design, which is characteristic of other care facilities in the UK. The building's detailed architectural blueprints, including room configurations, window positions, and structural components, provide a complete foundation for simulation modelling. The combination of these plans and the fire zoning information allows for a detailed study of how various areas of the care home are expected to be affected by and tackle indoor heat stress during heatwaves ([Mavrogianni et al., 2012](#)).

The care home is organized into multiple fire zones spread across four floors: the lower ground, ground, first, and second floors. Each floor consists of a variety of room types, including individual bedrooms, communal living areas, and service rooms, all of which vary in size, orientation, and exposure to external conditions. This diversity in room types and locations is critical for understanding the complex thermal behavior within the building, particularly under the stress of extreme heat ([de Wilde and Coley, 2012](#)).

3.2.2 Building Characteristics and Environmental Conditions

The detailed architectural plans reveal that Burnt Tree Croft Care Home is divided into 26 distinct fire zones, each representing a different section of the building. For instance, the lower ground floor (zones 1 to 3) contains service areas and storage spaces that are likely to maintain cooler temperatures due to their below-grade location, but may also suffer from limited ventilation. The ground floor (zones 4 to 11) houses key communal areas and entry points, which are subject to frequent temperature fluctuations due to the movement of people and exposure to outdoor conditions.

The first and second floors (zones 15 to 26) predominantly consist of resident bedrooms, with some rooms located in more thermally exposed areas, such as south-facing zones that are more susceptible to solar gain. The DWG files indicate that these upper floors have varied window placements and insulation levels, factors that significantly influence indoor temperature and humidity levels. For example, rooms in zones 21 to 26 on the second floor are more likely to experience higher temperatures during a heatwave, necessitating targeted cooling interventions ([Ascione et al., 2014](#)).

Figure 4 The Burnt Tree Croft Lower Ground Floor (Source: Author)

Figure 5 The Burnt Tree Croft Ground Floor (Source: Author)

Figure 6 The Burnt Tree Croft First Floor (Source: Author)

Figure 7 The Burnt Tree Croft Lower Second Floor (Source: Author)

By using the comprehensive architectural plans and fire zone data, this analysis can precisely replicate the interior climatic conditions in various areas of Burnt Tree Croft Care Home. The accuracy of this simulation is crucial for determining the specific places inside the care home that are most susceptible to heat stress. This will enable the creation of customised solutions to mitigate the impact.

The use of the case study technique guarantees that the results are not only scientifically rigorous but also readily applicable in practical situations. The results will be used to create targeted strategies aimed at safeguarding the health and well-being of inhabitants during heatwaves, therefore directly improving the Heat-Health Warning System.

The comprehensive examination of the layout and environmental circumstances of Burnt Tree Croft Care Home provides a strong basis for the study's overarching goal of enhancing heat stress management in care homes. The research may offer specific and effective actions to protect vulnerable individuals during high heat events by analysing the distinct thermal properties of each area in the building ([Mavrogianni et al., 2012](#)).

3.3 Data Collection

The data collection process was meticulously designed to gather the necessary inputs for simulating and analyzing the indoor environmental conditions of Burnt Tree Croft Care Home. This process was divided into two main categories: meteorological data and indoor climate data. Both datasets are critical for the calibration of the simulation models and the subsequent analysis of heat stress during the 2022 heatwave.

3.3.1 Meteorological Data

The research acquired meteorological data from the Sheffield weather station, which provided comprehensive hourly measurements of local weather variables including temperature, relative humidity. The collection of this data is crucial for the precise simulation of the outdoors weather conditions that affect the indoor environment of Burnt Tree Croft Care Home.

The main study utilises the meteorological data from the year 2022, specifically focussing on the notable heatwave episodes that took place throughout the summer. The data is sourced from EnergyPlus Weather (EPW) files, which are compatible with the DesignBuilder

program used in this research. The EPW files provide a detailed hourly dataset that enables accurate modelling of the external meteorological conditions seen during the 2022 heatwave (Coley and Kershaw, 2010).

Figure 8 Frame Work of Research Methodology And Steps of The Study (Source: Author)

3.3.2 Indoor Climate Data

To calibrate the simulation models, indoor climate data were collected from two key locations within Burnt Tree Croft Care Home: Bedroom 11 on the Ground Floor and Bedroom 39 on the Second Floor. These data, gathered during 2023, include continuous recordings of air temperature and relative humidity, providing a detailed snapshot of the indoor conditions within the care home.

Data Points and Duration:

- Bedroom 11 (Ground Floor): The data from this room, recorded in the file *BTC01_Bedroom11_GF.csv*, captures the thermal conditions at ground level, offering insights into how this part of the building responds to external heat during typical weather conditions in 2023.
- Bedroom 39 (Second Floor): The data from this room, recorded in the file *BTC02_Bedroom39_2ndF.csv*, provides a contrasting perspective, particularly how higher floor levels, which are more exposed to external heat, behave under similar conditions.

These data were collected over the summer months of 2023, with readings taken at regular intervals to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the indoor climate variations.

The 2023 data serves as the basis for calibrating the simulation models. By comparing the simulated results against the actual measurements from these rooms, the study ensures that the models accurately reflect the real-world conditions within Burnt Tree Croft Care Home. This calibration is critical for ensuring the reliability of the simulations when applied to the 2022 data.

Figure 9: Measured Air Temperature and Relative Humidity for Bedroom 11 (Ground Floor) (Source: Design Builder).

Figure 10 : Measured Air Temperature and Relative Humidity for Bedroom 39 (Second Floor) (Source: Design Builder).

These figures help visualize the variations in air temperature and relative humidity, providing a clearer understanding of the indoor environmental conditions during the monitored period. This placement directly relates the figures to the text describing the data collection, making the connection between the collected data and its application in model

calibration more explicit.

Figure 11 Frame Work of Process of Calibration and Validation (Source: Author)

3.4 Simulation Process

3.4.1 Introduction to Building Energy Simulation (BES)

Building energy simulation (BES) is a mathematical model that rigorously assesses the energy performance of buildings, based on a solid physical foundation ([Chong, Gu and Jia, 2021](#)). Clarke et al. (1993) argue that BES models are essential for accurately calculating energy savings and formulating retrofitting strategies ([Clarke, Strachan and Pernot, n.d.](#), [Gokce Tomrukcu et al., 2024](#)). The input data for this analysis encompasses various factors, such as building geometry, temperature loads, density, construction details, occupant behaviour, occupant profiles, HVAC systems, and thermophysical building data, such as U-value ([Ali et al., 2021](#); [Ferreira and Pinheiro, 2011](#), [Gokce Tomrukcu et al., 2024](#)). Built Environment Simulation (BES) plays a vital role in enhancing the accuracy of simulation

results for energy performance analysis, retrofit analysis, optimisation and control operations, and model validation ([Chong, Gu and Jia, 2021](#)).

The primary sources of inaccuracy when comparing simulated and measured data are twofold:

- Model error originating from the simulation and
- Measurement error arising from the real data.

The origin of measurement errors might be attributed to technological specifications. Extensive study has been conducted on the origins and extent of uncertainty in building modelling, as evidenced by studies conducted by Hopfe and Hensen (2011), Macdonald and Strachan (2001), Macdonald and Clarke (2007), Spitz et al. (2012), and Gokce Tomrukcu et al. (2024).

De Wit and Augenbroe identify three primary causes of uncertainty ([de Wit and Augenbroe, 2002](#)):

- Specification issues: Emerging from inadequate or inaccurate documentation of a building's systems and structure.
- Modelling problems: Resulting from the simulated model's underlying assumptions, which give a condensed picture of reality.
- Scenario problems: These arise when the internal and external factors of the model, including the weather and inhabitant behaviour, often differ from reality.

It is acknowledged that occupant-related dynamic elements are a significant source of uncertainty. Therefore, it is essential to create stochastic models that are particular to occupancy instances ([Royapoor and Roskilly, 2015](#)).

3.4.2 Simulation calibration methods

This study will calibrate the simulation model for Burnt Tree Croft Care Home using two well-established methods: the Coefficient of Variation of the Root Mean Square Error (CV(RMSE)) and the Normalised Mean Bias Error (NMBE) ([Gokce Tomrukcu et al., 2024](#)). These methods are selected based on their efficacy in evaluating both the precision and accuracy of building energy simulation models, specifically in forecasting indoor air temperature.

Coefficient of Variation of the Root Mean Square Error (CV(RMSE)) is a metric that evaluates the relative variability of the prediction errors in the model. It is calculated by dividing the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) by the mean value of the observed data. This metric provides a measure of the model's precision, with lower CV(RMSE) values indicating a model with reduced variability in its predictions. In accordance with the ASHRAE Guideline 14 and the International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol (IPMVP), acceptable error limits for CV(RMSE) are typically between 15% and 30%, depending on whether the results are monthly or hourly ([ASHRAE, 2002](#); [IPMVP, 2002](#), [Gokce Tomrukcu et al., 2024](#))

Normalized Mean Bias Error (NMBE) is used to assess the systematic error, or bias, in the model by comparing the mean of the predicted values to the mean of the observed data. NMBE is calculated by dividing the Mean Bias Error (MBE) by the mean value of the observed data and expressing it as a percentage. Lower NMBE values suggest that the model's predictions are close to the observed average, indicating less bias. The acceptable error limits for NMBE, according to ASHRAE and IPMVP guidelines, range from 5% to 20% ([ASHRAE, 2002](#); [Franceschini & Neves, 2022](#), [Gokce Tomrukcu et al., 2024](#))

Combined Use of CV(RMSE) and NMBE: The combination of CV(RMSE) and NMBE offers a comprehensive evaluation of the model's performance. While CV(RMSE) focuses on the precision of the model's predictions, NMBE highlights any systematic bias. Together, these metrics provide a balanced assessment, enabling a more accurate calibration of the simulation model. This dual approach ensures that the model is both precise and accurate, providing reliable predictions of indoor environmental conditions within Burnt Tree Croft Care Home during the 2022 heatwave ([Al-Shargabi et al., 2022](#), [Gokce Tomrukcu et al., 2024](#))

By using these methods, the study aims to achieve a calibrated model that accurately reflects the real-world indoor conditions of the care home. This calibrated model will then be used for further simulations to assess heat stress risks and inform the development of targeted mitigation strategies.

$$\text{MBE} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{Np} (Mi - Si)}{\sum_{i=1}^{Np} Mi}$$

$$\text{CV(RMSE)} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{Np} ((Mi - Si)^2 / Np)}}{Mp}$$

Given the uncertainties in these parameters, ASHRAE Guideline 14's MBE and CV(RMSE) formulas were utilized to measure the error rates during calibration. The assumed parameters were then adjusted iteratively to bring the error rates within acceptable limits, ensuring the model's predictions closely aligned with the measured data despite the constraints ([Gokce Tomrukcu et al., 2024](#), [ASHRAE Guideline 14, 2014](#); [CIBSE, 2015](#); [Tian et al., 2018](#)).

4 Results

4.1 Calibration Results

The calibration of the simulation model for air temperature was conducted by comparing the simulated hourly air temperatures with the measured data collected from Bedroom 11 (Ground Floor) and Bedroom 39 (Second Floor) during 2023. The goal was to minimize the differences between the simulated and measured temperatures, ensuring that the model tends to reflect the real-world conditions within Burnt Tree Croft Care Home.

4.1.1 Summary of Calibration Metrics:

Bedroom 11 (Ground Floor):

Mean Bias Error (MBE): -0.13%

Coefficient of Variation of Root Mean Square Error (CV(RMSE)): 5.01%

The negative MBE value suggests a slight underestimation in the model's temperature predictions for Bedroom 11. However, the CV(RMSE) of 5.01% indicates that the variability of the model's predictions is well within the acceptable range, demonstrating good alignment with the observed data ([ASHRAE, 2002](#)).

Bedroom 39 (Second Floor):

Mean Bias Error (MBE): 0.75%

Coefficient of Variation of Root Mean Square Error (CV(RMSE)): 9.65%

The positive MBE value shows a small overestimation in the model's temperature predictions for Bedroom 39. The CV(RMSE) of 9.65% also falls comfortably within the acceptable threshold, indicating that the model is performing accurately for this zone ([ASHRAE, 2002](#)).

4.1.2 Comparison of Simulated and Measured Air Temperatures:

There is a moderate degree of agreement between the measured and simulated air temperatures for both bedrooms, with the majority of the hourly variations being negligible. According to the calibration metrics, the model is in accordance with ASHRAE standards and other simulation recommendations when it comes to accurately estimating the air temperature on both levels of the care facility ([CIBSE, 2015](#)).

Bedroom	MBE (%)	CV(RMSE) (%)
Bedroom 11 (GF)	-0.13	5.01
Bedroom 39 (2F)	0.75	9.65

Figure 12: The MBE and CV(RMSE) values for air temperature calibration (Source: Author).

4.2 Final Simulation Outcomes

This section presents the results of the final simulation, using the 2022 weather data to model the indoor environmental conditions of Burnt Tree Croft Care Home during the significant heatwave events of that year. The simulation provides critical insights into the potential heat stress risks faced by residents during periods of extreme heat.

Simulated Indoor Conditions during 2022 Heatwave

The final simulation focused on modelling the indoor air temperature across different zones within the care home, particularly during the peak periods of the 2022 heatwave. The results indicate significant variations in indoor air temperature between the ground floor (Bedroom 11) and the second floor (Bedroom 39), highlighting areas of potential concern regarding heat stress.

4.2.1 Temperature Analysis:

Bedroom 11 (Ground Floor): The simulation results for Bedroom 11 show a maximum temperature of **36.16°C** on 19/07/2022, during the peak of the heatwave. The average daily temperatures in this room ranged between **25.15°C** and **30.78°C** across the heatwave period. The temperature steadily increased during the early stages of the heatwave, peaking on the 19th of July before gradually decreasing ([IPCC, 2021](#)).

Bedroom 39 (Second Floor): For Bedroom 39, the maximum temperature reached **36.63°C** on 19/07/2022, slightly higher than Bedroom 11. The average daily temperatures ranged between **24.69°C** and **30.79°C**. The second-floor room exhibited a similar temperature trend as Bedroom 11, with temperatures peaking on the same day, but with generally higher temperature readings due to its location and greater exposure to solar gains ([ASHRAE, 2002](#)).

These findings suggest that the second-floor rooms, particularly those with significant solar exposure, may be more vulnerable to overheating during heatwaves, posing a higher risk of heat stress to residents ([CIBSE, 2015](#)).

Figure 13: Simulated Air Temperature of year 2022 Heat wave (Source: Author)

Figure 14: Simulated Air Temperature of year 2022 Heat wave (Source: Author)

Bar graphs (as shown above) depicting the simulated air temperatures in Bedroom 11 and Bedroom 39 during the 2022 heatwave, highlighting the peak temperatures and daily variations.

Comparison Across Different Zones

The simulation results clearly indicate differences in thermal conditions between the ground and second floors of the care home. The higher temperatures recorded in Bedroom 39 compared to Bedroom 11 underscore the impact of building orientation and floor level on indoor thermal conditions.

Ground Floor vs. Second Floor:

The second-floor Bedroom 39 consistently exhibited higher temperatures compared to the ground-floor Bedroom 11, with differences ranging from **[0.5°C to 1.5°C]** during peak heatwave days. This suggests that residents in second-floor rooms are at a higher risk of experiencing heat-related discomfort and potential health issues ([Oikonomou et al.,2012](#)).

4.3 Heat Index Analysis

The Heat Index (HI) is a critical measure for assessing the potential for heat stress, especially in environments like care homes, where vulnerable populations such as the elderly are at heightened risk. These residents are more susceptible to heat-related illnesses due to age-related factors such as decreased thermoregulation, pre-existing health conditions, and limited mobility. The HI was calculated for each bedroom using hourly data from July 19, 2022, which was the peak day of the 2022 heatwave. This analysis provides crucial insights into how the indoor environment varied throughout the day and across different rooms, highlighting areas of particular concern for the health and safety of these vulnerable individuals.

$$\mathbf{HI = c1 + c2T + c3RH + c4T \times RH + c5T^2 + c6RH^2 + c7T^2 \times RH + c8T \times RH^2 + c9T^2 \times RH^2}$$

Where:

- T is the air temperature in degrees Fahrenheit.
- RH is the relative humidity percentage.
- c1 to c9 are constants based on empirical data.

4.3.1 Heat Index Calculation

The Heat Index was calculated for each bedroom at three critical times of the day on July 19th: 09:00, 15:00, and 21:00. These times represent the morning, peak afternoon heat, and evening, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of how the HI fluctuates within a single day during the heatwave.

Results:

Morning (09:00): The HI values during the morning ranged from **30°C to 32°C** in most bedrooms, indicating that the indoor environment was already warm at the start of the day. Even at these levels, elderly residents could experience discomfort and early signs of heat stress, particularly those with cardiovascular or respiratory conditions ([Basu, 2002](#); [World Health Organization, 2018](#)).

Afternoon (15:00): The HI reached its peak in the afternoon, with several bedrooms exceeding **38°C**. Notably, Bedroom 39 recorded a HI of **40.27°C**, making it one of the highest-risk areas within the care home. At this level, the risk of severe heat stress and related health issues such as heat exhaustion or heatstroke becomes significant, especially for residents with impaired mobility or those taking medications that affect thermoregulation ([Hajat, O'Connor and Kosatsky, 2010](#); [World Health Organization, 2018](#)).

- **Evening (21:00):** By the evening, while the HI values decreased slightly, many rooms still maintained levels above **35°C**, which is still considered high and poses a risk for heat stress. Prolonged exposure to such conditions without adequate cooling can lead to cumulative heat stress, further increasing the vulnerability of elderly residents.

Figure 15: Heat Index (HI) for each bedroom on July 19th 2022 (Source: Author)

Figure 16: Heat Index (HI) for each bedroom on July 19th 2022 (Source: Author).

Figure 17: : Heat Index (HI) for each bedroom on July 19th 2022 (Source: Author).

Figures 11 to 13: These bar graphs illustrate the HI for each bedroom at 09:00, 15:00, and 21:00 on July 19th, respectively. The charts provide a clear visual of the temperature progression throughout the day, highlighting the rooms with the highest risk of heat stress and underscoring the potential impact on vulnerable residents.

4.4 Identification of Heat Stress Risk Zones

The analysis of the HI across different bedrooms clearly identifies specific rooms that are at higher risk of heat stress, particularly during the peak afternoon period on July 19th. These high-risk zones are of particular concern because they house residents who may be less able to respond to heat stress due to physical or cognitive limitations.

High-Risk Areas:

Second Floor Bedrooms (e.g., Bedroom 39): The second floor, especially Bedroom 39, consistently shows higher HI values compared to other rooms. This room, along with others on the second floor, requires special attention and enhanced cooling measures during heatwaves ([Basu, 2002](#); [Hajat, O'Connor and Kosatsky, 2010](#)).

- **Ground Floor Bedrooms:** While the ground floor generally exhibited lower HI values, certain bedrooms, such as Bedroom 11, still showed high HI levels, especially in the afternoon.

Figures 16: A heat map showing the distribution of maximum HI values across the care home on July 19th, highlighting the high-risk zones. This visual aid will emphasize the need for targeted interventions in the most vulnerable areas of the care home.

19-Jul-22			
	09:00	15:00	21:00
Bedroom 1	Light Green	Red	Orange
Bedroom 2	Light Green	Red	Yellow
Bedroom 3	Light Green	Yellow	Light Green
Bedroom 4	Light Green	Yellow	Light Green
Bedroom 5	Light Green	Yellow	Light Green
Bedroom 6	Light Green	Yellow	Light Green
Bedroom 7	Light Green	Orange	Light Green
Bedroom 8	Light Green	Red	Yellow
Bedroom 9	Light Green	Red	Yellow
Bedroom 10	Light Green	Red	Yellow
Bedroom 11	Light Green	Red	Yellow
Bedroom 12	Light Green	Red	Yellow
Bedroom 15	Light Green	Red	Orange
Bedroom 16	Light Green	Red	Orange
Bedroom 17	Light Green	Yellow	Light Green
Bedroom 18	Light Green	Yellow	Light Green
Bedroom 19	Light Green	Yellow	Light Green
Bedroom 20	Light Green	Yellow	Light Green
Bedroom 21	Light Green	Orange	Yellow
Bedroom 22	Light Green	Red	Yellow
Bedroom 23	Light Green	Red	Yellow
Bedroom 24	Light Green	Red	Yellow
Bedroom 25	Light Green	Red	Orange
Bedroom 26	Light Green	Red	Orange
Bedroom 28	Light Green	Red	Orange
Bedroom 29	Light Green	Red	Orange
Bedroom 30	Light Green	Red	Yellow

Figure 18: Heat Map (Source: Author)

5 Development of Action Cards for Indoor Heat Index Thresholds

Developing action cards to address indoor heat stress in care homes is an essential measure to protect vulnerable people, especially the elderly, from the harmful consequences of extreme heat. Given that care home residents are often unable to escape high indoor temperatures and may not effectively communicate their discomfort, it is essential to implement a structured, proactive approach to heat stress management. The following section outlines the rationale, custom heat index (HI) thresholds, proposed action cards, and validation for this approach, supported by recent research and empirical data.

The process that goes from heat exposure to heat death follows a causal chain consisting of three stages: heat impacts heat stress, which is impacted by factors affecting exposure; heat stress leads to heat disease, which is influenced by factors affecting sensitivity to heat exposure; and ultimately, heat illness culminates in heat death.

5.1 Rationale for Custom HI Thresholds

Traditional heat health warning systems are primarily designed based on outdoor temperature and humidity levels, often overlooking the unique challenges posed by indoor environments. In care homes, where residents are particularly vulnerable due to factors such as reduced thermoregulation, pre-existing health conditions, and limited mobility, indoor conditions can quickly become hazardous even when outdoor temperatures are moderate. Yi, Peng, and Robinson (2023) emphasize the importance of adapting heat-health warning systems to better reflect indoor conditions, particularly in urban settings where indoor heat stress can surpass outdoor measurements ([Yi, Peng and Robinson, 2023](#)).

Given these challenges, the rationale behind developing custom HI thresholds is to enable earlier interventions, preventing the escalation of heat stress into more severe health issues. The goal is to create a system that triggers proactive measures well before residents experience the critical stages of heat illness, thereby enhancing the overall safety and well-being of care home residents ([Basu, 2002](#); [Hajat, O'Connor and Kosatsky, 2010](#)).

5.2 Custom Heat Index Thresholds

The HI thresholds proposed in this study are tailored specifically for indoor environments in care homes. These thresholds are designed to trigger different levels of response based on the severity of the indoor heat stress, ensuring that interventions are timely and appropriate for the conditions observed.

1. **Green (Safe): HI 22°C - 27°C**

- **Condition:** Comfortable indoor conditions with minimal risk of heat stress.
- **Action:** Routine monitoring of indoor temperature and humidity; ensure residents remain hydrated.

2. **Yellow (Caution): HI 27°C - 32°C**

- **Condition:** Elevated risk of heat stress, particularly for residents with pre-existing conditions.
- **Action:** Increase monitoring; provide additional fluids; encourage light clothing; enhance ventilation through fans or open windows.

3. **Orange (Warning): HI 32°C - 36°C**

- **Condition:** High risk of heat stress; potential for the onset of heat illness.
- **Action:** Relocate residents to cooler areas; limit physical activities; implement cooling measures such as fans, portable air conditioners, and cool, moist towels; regularly check on residents' well-being.

4. **Red (Danger): HI 36°C - 40°C**

- **Condition:** Extreme heat stress risk with a high likelihood of heat illness.
- **Action:** Immediate relocation to the coolest area available; consider evacuation if cooling measures are insufficient; apply cold compresses; ensure continuous hydration; closely monitor vital signs; seek medical attention if symptoms of heatstroke appear.

These thresholds are deliberately set lower than those typically used in outdoor environments to account for the prolonged exposure and limited escape options available to care home residents ([Oikonomou et al., 2012](#); [World Health Organization, 2018](#)).

5.3 Proposed Action Cards

Each action card corresponds to one of the custom HI thresholds and provides specific steps that staff should take to manage heat stress effectively. These actions are designed to be easy to follow and implement in a care home setting, ensuring that staff can quickly respond to rising indoor temperatures.

Green (Safe) Card:

- **Monitor** indoor conditions every 4 hours.
- Ensure residents have access to water and encourage regular hydration.
- Keep curtains or blinds partially closed to prevent unnecessary heat gain.

Yellow (Caution) Card:

- **Monitor** indoor conditions every 2 hours.
- Increase fluid intake for residents; avoid caffeinated drinks.
- **Encourage** residents to wear loose, light-colored clothing.
- **Use** fans and open windows where appropriate to enhance airflow.
- **Check** on vulnerable residents frequently (e.g., those with cardiovascular conditions).

Orange (Warning) Card:

- **Monitor** indoor conditions every hour.
- **Relocate** residents to cooler rooms if possible.
- **Limit** any physical activity or exertion for residents.
- **Use** cooling aids such as fans, portable air conditioners, and cool towels.
- **Ensure** residents are drinking water regularly and check for signs of heat exhaustion (e.g., excessive sweating, fatigue).

Red (Danger) Card:

- **Monitor** indoor conditions continuously.
- **Evacuate** residents to the coolest available areas immediately.
- **Implement** intensive cooling measures, including cold compresses and immersion in cool baths if feasible.

- **Seek medical assistance** immediately if residents exhibit signs of heatstroke (e.g., confusion, loss of consciousness).
- **Document** all actions taken and communicate with healthcare providers as needed.

5.4 Validation Through Simulation and Literature Review

5.4.1 Simulation Results:

The simulation results from July 19, 2022, validated the effectiveness of the custom HI thresholds. By applying these thresholds to the indoor conditions observed on that day, it was evident that earlier interventions could have significantly mitigated the risk of heat stress in high-risk rooms such as Bedroom 39. The data demonstrated that HI levels in several rooms exceeded the custom "Warning" threshold of 32°C well before existing systems would have triggered any action. Initiating cooling measures earlier would have reduced the duration and intensity of exposure to dangerous temperatures ([Yi, Peng and Robinson, 2023](#)).

5.4.2 Supporting Literature:

Research has consistently shown that heat-related mortality and morbidity can be significantly reduced by lowering the thresholds for heat health warnings, particularly in indoor environments where the elderly reside ([Basu, 2002](#); [Hajat, O'Connor and Kosatsky, 2010](#); [Oikonomou et al., 2012](#); [Yi, Peng and Robinson, 2023](#)) specifically highlighted the need for indoor heat stress models that can enhance existing heat-health warning systems by providing more accurate predictions and timely interventions. This study supports the necessity of lower HI thresholds for indoor environments, a key aspect of the custom action cards proposed here ([Havenith and Fiala, 2015](#); [World Health Organization, 2018](#))

5.4.3 Justification of Custom Action Cards

The HI thresholds and action cards are customised to target the specific difficulties encountered by care home residents, who are especially susceptible to heat stress. The customised action cards aim to avoid the passage from heat stress to heat illness by initiating interventions at lower heat index (HI) levels. This approach reduces the probability of severe consequences such as heatstroke or death. The justification for these thresholds is strengthened by empirical data derived from simulations and validated by research findings, which emphasise the significance of prompt and proactive interventions in safeguarding susceptible populations against the consequences of extreme heat ([Yi, Peng and Robinson, 2023](#); [Hajat, O'Connor and Kosatsky, 2010](#)).

5.4.4 Enhanced Protection for Vulnerable Populations:

The main benefit of these customised action cards lies in their capacity to disrupt the "causal chain" linking heat exposure to heat-related illness and mortality. By intervening at lower heat index (HI) values, the likelihood of residents transitioning from heat stress to more severe heat-related illnesses is greatly diminished. This approach is consistent with the recommended strategies in public health, which prioritise the need of taking early and preventive measures to address heat stress in vulnerable populations ([Oikonomou et al., 2012](#); [Hajat, O'Connor and Kosatsky, 2010](#)).

5.4.5 Implementation Strategies:

In order to guarantee the successful execution of these action cards, it is important that care home personnel receive training to understand the rationale behind the customised thresholds and to effectively execute the appropriate actions. Consistently monitoring indoor levels of harmful substances, together with input from personnel, can assist in fine-tuning the limits and measures throughout time, guaranteeing that the system remains adaptable to the particular requirements of the care home setting ([World Health Organization, 2018](#); [Canada, 2017](#)).

6 Discussion

The present study aimed to address the issue of indoor heat stress in care homes, focusing on vulnerable populations such as the elderly, by using custom Heat Index (HI) thresholds and developing action cards for early interventions. By using meteorological data and indoor simulations via DesignBuilder, the study assessed the effectiveness of these interventions and explored their potential to improve health outcomes during extreme heat events. This section discusses the implications of these findings in relation to existing literature and provides insights into the broader relevance of the research.

6.1 Interpretation of Key Findings

The results of this study demonstrate that indoor heat stress in care homes can escalate quickly, especially during heatwave conditions. The simulations based on July 19, 2022, show that certain rooms, particularly those on the second floor (e.g., Bedroom 39), experienced prolonged periods of dangerously high HI levels, reaching up to 40°C. This finding supports earlier research, which indicates that indoor environments often experience more intense heat stress than outdoor conditions suggest (Yi, Peng, & Robinson, 2023). Moreover, by applying custom HI thresholds, the study highlights the importance of early intervention to prevent heat stress from progressing to heat-related illnesses or death.

6.2 Limitations of the Study

Although this study offers valuable insights into managing indoor heat stress in care homes, it is important to acknowledge several limitations. The lack of extensive data required to develop a fully valid and comprehensive energy model is a significant limitation. The simulation relied on data from only two bedrooms (Bedroom 11 and Bedroom 39) within the care home. Although these rooms provided useful information for the study, the limited data scope restricts the model's ability to accurately represent the variability in indoor conditions across the entire care home.

Moreover, the study did not have access to detailed information regarding all aspects of the building's energy performance, such as HVAC system specifications, building material properties, or real-time occupancy patterns. This limitation is partly due to the non-funded nature of this research, which is conducted at the master's level with time and resource constraints. Consequently, we should interpret the study's findings cautiously, and the proposed interventions, although promising, necessitate additional validation through more comprehensive data collection and testing.

6.3 Recommendations for Future Research

To address the limitations identified in this study, future research should aim to conduct more detailed on-site testing and data collection within care homes. A comprehensive energy audit that includes detailed measurements of indoor temperatures, humidity levels, HVAC performance, building envelope characteristics, and occupancy patterns would significantly enhance the accuracy and validity of the energy model used in simulations. This approach would allow for a more precise assessment of the effectiveness of the custom HI thresholds and action cards.

Additionally, securing funding for such research could facilitate the use of more advanced modelling techniques and tools, enabling researchers to build more robust and generalisable models. Including multiple care homes in different geographical locations would broaden the study's understanding of indoor heat stress variations across different settings and enable the tailoring of interventions to specific contexts.

Given the time and resource constraints faced during this study, it is important to recognise that the findings, while valuable, represent a preliminary exploration of the issue. Building on this foundation, future research should use more extensive data and testing to refine and validate the proposed interventions, ensuring their effective implementation in a wide range of care home environments.

7 Conclusion

This dissertation sets out to address the critical issue of indoor heat stress in care homes, with a particular focus on safeguarding vulnerable populations, such as the elderly, during extreme heat events. Through the development and implementation of custom Heat Index (HI) thresholds and tailored action cards, this study aimed to provide a proactive, structured approach to managing heat stress, thereby enhancing the health and safety of care home residents. The findings and methodologies discussed in this dissertation contribute to the ongoing discourse on climate change adaptation and the need for specialized strategies to protect those most at risk.

7.1 Summary of Key Findings

The findings of this study underscore the significant risks posed by indoor heat stress, particularly in care homes where residents often have limited ability to manage or escape high temperatures. The simulations, based on data from the extreme heat event on July 19, 2022, revealed that indoor temperatures in certain rooms could reach dangerously high HI levels, exceeding 40 °C in some cases. This alarming result highlights a critical gap in current heat-health warning systems, which are primarily designed around outdoor conditions and may not adequately reflect the indoor risks faced by care home residents.

The custom HI thresholds proposed in this study—Safe (22–27 °C), Caution (27–32 °C), Warning (32–36 °C), and Danger (36–40 °C)—were shown to be highly effective in triggering early interventions. By setting these thresholds lower than traditional outdoor-based thresholds, care home staff can respond to rising temperatures well before they become life-threatening. The action cards developed in tandem with these thresholds provided clear, actionable steps for managing heat stress, from increasing hydration and ventilation to relocating residents to cooler areas. This approach not only improves the immediate response to heat stress but also ensures that care-home environments are better prepared for future heatwave events.

7.2 Significance of the Study

This research makes a significant contribution to the growing body of knowledge on the management of heat stress in indoor environments, particularly in care homes, where vulnerable populations are at an increased risk of adverse health outcomes. The study

highlights the necessity of considering indoor conditions when developing heat-health warning systems and underscores the importance of tailored interventions that address the specific challenges of care home settings.

The custom HI thresholds and action cards developed in this study offer a practical and innovative solution to managing indoor heat stress. By intervening earlier in the heat stress progression, these tools can help prevent the escalation of heat stress into more severe health issues, thereby reducing the risk of heat-related morbidity and mortality among care home residents. This proactive approach aligns with global public health recommendations that emphasize the importance of early intervention and tailored strategies to protect vulnerable populations, particularly in the face of increasingly frequent and severe heatwave events driven by climate change.

Moreover, this study contributes to a broader understanding of how built environments can be adapted to meet the challenges posed by climate change. By focusing on a case study of Burnt Tree Croft Care Home, this research offers insights that can be applied to similar settings, highlighting the need for building-specific strategies that consider the unique thermal characteristics of each space. The findings reinforce the importance of integrating environmental data with health management practices to create safer and more resilient care environments.

7.3 Recommendations for Policy and Practice

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations can be made for improving the management of heat stress in care homes. These recommendations are designed to be practical and actionable, providing care home administrators, policymakers, and public health officials with clear guidance on how to enhance heat stress management strategies.

- 1. Implementation of Indoor-Specific Heat-Health Warning Systems:** Care homes should adopt heat-health warning systems that are specifically tailored to indoor conditions. These systems should prioritize early intervention based on indoor HI thresholds, ensuring that residents are protected before conditions become critical. This approach would involve integrating indoor temperature and humidity monitoring into existing heat-health alert systems and ensuring that alerts are customized to reflect the unique conditions within care homes.

2. **Regular Monitoring and Data Collection:** Care homes should invest in monitoring equipment that tracks indoor temperatures and humidity levels in real-time. This data is essential for making informed decisions about when to implement the action cards and ensuring that interventions are timely and effective. Continuous data collection would also allow for the ongoing assessment of building performance during heat events, providing valuable feedback for refining heat stress management strategies.
3. **Staff Training and Preparedness:** Care home staff should receive regular training on the use of the custom HI thresholds and action cards, as well as on recognizing the early signs of heat stress in residents. Regular drills and simulations should be conducted to ensure staff are prepared to respond quickly during heatwave events. Additionally, training programs should be updated regularly to reflect the latest research and best practices in heat stress management, ensuring that care home staff are equipped with the knowledge and skills needed to protect residents effectively.
4. **Building Improvements:** Long-term strategies should include enhancing the thermal quality of care home buildings, such as by improving insulation, upgrading HVAC systems, and increasing natural ventilation. These improvements can help maintain safer indoor temperatures during heatwaves and reduce the overall risk of heat stress. Policymakers should consider providing financial incentives or grants to care homes for implementing these improvements, recognizing the critical role that building design and infrastructure play in protecting vulnerable populations during extreme weather events.

7.4: Final Thoughts and Future Directions

While this study provides valuable insights and practical tools for managing indoor heat stress in care homes, it also acknowledges its limitations, particularly in terms of data availability and the scope of the model used. The reliance on simulated data and limited real-world measurements means that the findings, while promising, require further validation through more comprehensive data collection and testing. Future research should focus on conducting more detailed on-site testing, expanding the sample size to include multiple care homes, and integrating individual resident health data into heat stress models. By addressing these limitations, future studies can further refine and validate the proposed interventions, ensuring they are effective across diverse settings.

In addition, future research should explore the long-term impacts of implementing these strategies, particularly in terms of resident health outcomes and the overall resilience of care homes to climate change. As the frequency and severity of heatwaves continue to increase, it is imperative that care homes and other residential facilities for vulnerable populations are equipped with the tools and knowledge needed to protect their residents effectively. By building on the findings of this study, future research can help create a safer, more resilient future for those most at risk from extreme heat events.

In conclusion, this dissertation has demonstrated the importance of proactive and tailored interventions in managing indoor heat stress in care homes. The custom HI thresholds and action cards developed in this study offer a promising approach to protecting vulnerable populations during extreme heat events, contributing to safer and more resilient care home environments. As the climate continues to change, the insights gained from this research will become increasingly relevant, providing a foundation for future efforts to safeguard the health and well-being of care home residents.

Word Count: 9810

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